

LEGAL REGULATION OF THE USE OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

This study addresses the role of authorities in regulating the use of digital intelligence technology, paving the way for the optimal use of artificial intelligence systems, software, and applications in a manner that is objective, transparent, secure, and confidential. This study takes into account the user's right to privacy and expression, while seeking to avoid the risks and harms that may arise from the rapid and unprecedented development of these technologies and their applications. This necessitates those competent national authorities enact a legal framework capable of adequately regulating the uses of digital intelligence without infringing on the rights of others. Such a framework must include legislation, regulations, administrative directives, and decisions, as well as empower the judiciary to issue relevant judgments and compensate those harmed by the use of such technologies, and impose penalties on violators of the law and public order. It also highlights the government's role in developing policies, strategies, and mechanisms for implementing and achieving the objectives of regulation and institutional development, in accordance with globally recognized norms and ethics of the use of artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Legal Regulation, Technology, Digital Intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

The role of authorities in regulating the use of digital intelligence technology is one of the most important topics that confronts researchers with the legitimacy of this new technology in general. This is especially true given the developments and changes related to what is now termed "digital intelligence," which has permeated all areas of political, economic, social, medical, judicial, and scientific life. This requires national and international authorities to develop policies, strategies, and executive and security mechanisms that enable users—individuals, companies, institutions, and international and local organizations—to use it legally and safely.

The second half of the twentieth century witnessed significant technological developments marked by the emergence of new means of communication. This was then called modern information and communication technology (ICT) marked by the emergence the use of electronic computers to store, analyze, and retrieve information. This evolution, further propelled by the spread of the internet, digital communications, satellites, and fiber optics, ultimately led to what is now commonly referred to as artificial intelligence. Since the 1980s, and particularly from 1984 onward, various legal analyses have been undertaken to address the development and use of AI applications and technologies—efforts that continue to the present day.

Legal regulation of the use of digital intelligence technology is an urgent necessity in the virtual world, as the law performs important functions for all segments of society, starting with the provision of public services and the protection of all societal components without discrimination, and culminating in monitoring and regulation.

Digital intelligence technologies inherently lack understanding of the prevailing moral values, societal norms, and ethical standards. They are mere deaf devices devoid of human emotions and the natural intelligence needed to understand, perceive, and rationally engage with the circumstances and surroundings. Countries using these technologies are required to enact and issue laws and regulations governing these applications, as well as requiring licenses for their ownership or use. Furthermore, the commitment of the parties using them to legal and ethical controls is a key condition for making appropriate decisions regarding them. Article (17) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights states:

"No one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home, or correspondence."

Therefore, digital intelligence threatens individuals' privacy, blurring the boundaries between private and public life¹.

Accordingly, state-level enforcement actions against the unregulated dissemination of AI systems and applications are of critical importance, particularly given that AI effectively operates as a digital mind². Therefore, data and information are shared with segments of society either proactively through the open government data platform on the e-government portal and government agency websites, or interactively through paper and electronic access to information requests³. Thus, the information revolution, in conjunction with the communications revolution, creates a vast and expansive world in various social, economic, political, cultural, and other fields. Perhaps the emergence of commercial transactions and contracts between individuals and companies has become increasingly complex in light of the widespread use of digital (artificial) intelligence systems and software, necessitating the establishment of a robust legal framework to govern all such activities.

The Problem of the Study

The core issue addressed by this study is the role played by the relevant authorities, whether from the government or the legislature, in creating an appropriate legal structure for issuing laws governing the use and protection of digital intelligence applications and technologies, in line with the ethical principles and values that govern their use and determine liability for damages resulting from their implementation.

Study Questions:

1. What is the legal basis for holding users of digital intelligence technology accountable?
2. What role does the legislature play in regulating the use of digital intelligence technologies?

Study Objectives

1. To clarify the legal regulation and implementation mechanisms for the use of digital intelligence systems by authorities.
2. To regulate safe and effective applications of digital intelligence systems.

Study Methodology

The researcher adopted a descriptive and analytical approach in his study of this topic entitled: "*The Role of Authorities in Regulating the Use of Digital Intelligence Technology.*" This approach requires the description, analysis, and evaluation of the role played by legislators and government authorities in formulating the regulatory legal framework governing such technologies.

CHAPTER ONE: THE NATURE OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY

This chapter addresses the nature of digital intelligence technology through three main topics:

- **Section One:** The Concept of Digital Intelligence
- **Section Two:** Fields of Application for Digital Intelligence
- **Section Three:** The Importance of Applying Digital Intelligence Technology

Section One: The Concept of Digital Intelligence

This section will define digital intelligence, its characteristics, and its types.

First: Definition of Digital Intelligence

Numerous terms and definitions have emerged for *digital intelligence* or *artificial intelligence* (AI). Legal scholars and researchers have proposed various definitions, yet they generally converge on a central concept. Among them is:

*"The ability of machines and digital computers to perform specific tasks that simulate those carried out by intelligent beings, such as thinking, learning from past experiences, or other processes that require cognitive functions."*⁴

Another definition of digital intelligence is: "The use of digital technology to create systems capable of performing tasks that mimic human mental abilities and patterns of operation, analyze the surrounding environment, learn from errors, and make predictions or forecasts, provide recommendations, make decisions, or take actions that impact real or virtual environments with a degree of autonomy."⁵

Some have defined it as: "A part of computer science that aims to design intelligent systems that enable computers to represent and mimic human thinking and some human behavioral capabilities, giving them the same characteristics, we know as intelligence in human behavior."

In the memorandum of the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (Fifty-first session) for the year 2018, it was stated that: "*Several definitions of artificial*

intelligence have been proposed, yet none has achieved universal acceptance. Generally, artificial intelligence refers to the development of systems capable of solving problems and performing functions by mimicking cognitive processes.....”⁶

The first and second paragraphs of US Executive Order No. 13859 of 2019 define *open data* as: “Data that is made available to the public and structured in a way that is fully discoverable and usable by end users.”

In France, the government launched its National Artificial Intelligence Strategy in 2017, which led to the establishment of the National Consultative Ethics Committee. This committee defined AI as:

“A computer system dedicated to performing tasks that are currently most satisfyingly performed by humans because they require high-level mental processes such as perceptual learning, memory organization, and critical thinking. These processes therefore presuppose cognitive abilities that allow it to achieve goals independently.”⁷

This definition highlights the extent to which artificial intelligence is closely linked to current human achievements. However, it has been criticized for not taking into account the rapid development of artificial intelligence, which poses a significant risk if it surpasses the human mind in accomplishing its tasks.

The United Nations defines digital intelligence as: *“A discipline in computer science that aims to develop machines and systems capable of performing tasks perceived as requiring human intelligence, with or without limited human intervention.”⁸*

The Council of Ministers approved the Jordanian Artificial Intelligence Policy in 2020 and circulated it to ministries, institutions, and government departments for compliance. This policy is consistent with the requirements of the 2018 General Policy for the Information and Communications Technology and Postal Sector. It aims to define the government's direction in the field of artificial intelligence in all vital economic sectors, and to create an enabling environment for artificial intelligence from the legislative, regulatory, and technological aspects, as well as to build Jordanian capabilities and skills in this domain.⁹

Article Two of the Jordanian Electronic Transactions Law No. (15) of 2015 defines an electronic intermediary as: *“The electronic program that is used to automatically perform or respond to an action with the intent of creating, sending, or receiving an information message.”*

Based on these definitions, **digital intelligence** can be defined as:

“The science that enables industrial machines, through computer programs, to perform operations that require special intelligence that mimics the human mind and behavior.”

Accordingly, legal scholars have turned to researching multiple issues that impact legislators' approach, seeking to develop laws and regulations to keep pace with and address errors or behavior that may arise from the use of advanced technology applications, which may result in legal accountability. This includes addressing damages resulting from the activation of the use of artificial intelligence applications to serve

individuals, including the establishment of jurisdiction over the scope of contractual liability.⁹

Second: Characteristics of Digital Intelligence Technology:

Digital intelligence technology is characterized by a set of unique characteristics and features, whether in terms of thinking and perception, understanding and creativity, analysis and implementation, as well as the ability to explore and employ new situations, deal with complex situations, and resolve them with extreme precision¹⁰. However, it lacks human values, principles, ethics, and emotions, especially when used in wars, conflicts, and the commission of crimes. Various crimes.

Third: Types of Digital Intelligence:

There are three types of digital intelligence systems known globally, and they are divided into the following:¹¹

1. Limited-scope digital intelligence.
2. General digital intelligence.
3. High-precision digital intelligence.

It is well known that the aforementioned digital intelligence systems operate independently of their operators or programmers, as each of these three types of systems will be processed separately.

1. Limited-scope digital intelligence:

Limited-scope digital intelligence gives a machine the ability to understand, analyze, comply with, and implement commands, such as facial, image, and voice recognition programs. What distinguishes it from other systems is its limited scope, as it cannot deviate from the tasks for which it was pre-programmed, thus remaining within the scope of predicting its actions and the possibility of controlling it.

2. General digital intelligence:

General digital intelligence operates with a capacity similar to human thinking; it enables a machine to think and plan on its own in a manner similar to human behavior. Applications of this form include research into the development of artificial neural networks for industrial robots designed to emulate the biological neural systems of the human body.

3. High-precision digital intelligence.

High-precision digital intelligence transcends the limits of human intelligence, enabling it to perform tasks and powers better than those of specialized humans, thanks to its learning technology. Digital intelligence has many unique features, including the ability to learn, plan, communicate automatically, and make judgments and decisions quickly and independently.

From the above, it is clear that limited-scope digital intelligence is the most common and abundant type in the current era, unlike high-precision digital intelligence, which is still considered a hypothetical concept with no presence in the realm of hypothetical and limited applied research within laboratories and scientific research centers.

Third Section: The Importance of Applying Digital Intelligence Technology:

Numerous advantages can be realized through the use of modern technologies and machines based on advanced science, high-precision programming, efficiency, and reliability. These intelligent technologies are now applied across many sectors of life, including machine learning, aircraft piloting, traffic control, complex surgical operations, precision electronics industries, heavy machinery, vehicle management, and more. This technology is also being used in the field of leveling. Online dispute resolution and conference organization.

Moreover, this technology is increasingly used in online dispute resolution, virtual conference organization¹², administrative procedures, automated tax settlements, debt collection, and the issuance of administrative decisions. These include intelligent communication between officials and subordinates, as well as between citizens and governments. Collectively, these applications enhance the quality of services provided by government bodies that employ digital technology.

CHAPTER TWO: LEGISLATIVE REGULATION OF THE USE OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY

Today, the discussion revolves around personal data, its privacy, and its processing by special electronic systems affiliated with various state agencies and departments, as well as who has the right to disclose this data.

Article 8 of the European Union Charter on Fundamental Human Rights, which is crucial to the use of artificial intelligence, stipulates the right to information self-determination and data protection.¹³

According to the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**—which came into force in 2018 and applies to both governmental bodies and private sector entities within the European Union—the following core principles must be observed when processing personal data, namely:

1. Transparency and clarity in communication with users.
2. Restriction Objectives
3. Data Minimization
4. Accuracy and Proficiency
5. Storage Restrictions
6. Integrity and Objectivity, avoiding sensitive data such as race, political opinions, religion, health status, gender, and genetic data.

7. Strict confidentiality.
8. The necessity of responding to user requests to access, correct, or delete their data.
9. The right to object.
10. Big Data Analysis.

In this regard, Article (68) of the Egyptian Constitution of 2014 stipulates that:

“Information, data, statistics, and official documents are the property of the people. Disclosure thereof from various sources is a right guaranteed by the state to every citizen. The state is obliged to provide and make such information available transparently. The law shall regulate the rules for accessing, disclosing, preserving, and appealing the withholding of information, and shall also determine the penalties for the intentional withholding of or provision of false information.”

We conclude by saying that the right to privacy and confidentiality of personal data is a focus of most international legislation and conventions, which requires its protection and prohibition of its misuse under laws and regulations related to digital intelligence.

Accordingly, we will address this topic through two sections:

The First Section: The Impact of The Use of Digital Intelligence Technology on Personal Data

Legislators have granted entities responsible for developing digital intelligence software the authority to input and manage various types of data—be it personal, commercial, legal, medical, political, or, otherwise. Those processing this data must be neutral and objective, and may not favor one party, group, individual, or entity over another. Digital intelligence systems are not merely pure information and data; they also have significant social, political, legal, and aesthetic dimensions.¹⁴

In 2020, Jordan’s Council of Ministers approved the **National Artificial Intelligence Policy**, requiring all ministries, institutions, and government departments to adhere to its provisions. This policy aligns with the **General Policy for the Telecommunications, Information Technology, and Postal Sector (2018)** and seeks to define the government’s strategic direction in AI across vital economic sectors, and to create an enabling environment for artificial intelligence from the legislative, regulatory, and technological perspectives, as well as to build Jordanian capacities and skills in this field.

Pursuant to Article (31) of the Jordanian Constitution, as amended in 2022, the Personal Data Protection Law No. (24) of 2023 was issued. Article 2 defines personal data as: *“Any data or information related to a natural person that can identify them, directly or indirectly, regardless of their source or form, including data related to their person, marital status, or location.”*

The same article referred to above also defines processing as: *“One or more operations carried out in any form or by any means with the aim of collecting, recording, copying,*

saving, storing, organizing, purifying, exploiting, using, sending, distributing, publishing, linking it to other data, making it available, transferring, displaying, or Concealing, encoding, destroying, restricting, erasing, modifying, characterizing, or disclosing data by any means." The definition of a data processor is also stated as: "A natural or legal person who is competent to process data."

It should be noted that the data processor is the one who has the right to input, output, and process data. Therefore, the legislative authority must impose regulatory provisions that achieve the public interest.

Otherwise, data processing and development processes are undemocratic, unfair, and lack transparency, raising numerous concerns about the rule of law and endangering individual rights and freedoms.

Therefore, digital intelligence systems must not be allowed to operate without oversight or monitoring, and they must not be allowed to issue decisions and rulings in lieu of their legally authorized owners. Accordingly, Article (16) stipulates the formation of a council called the Personal Data Protection Council, headed by the Minister of Digital Economy and Entrepreneurship, and a number of members, including the Commissioner-General for Human Rights, a representative of the Central Bank, representatives of the security services, and others. The council is tasked with formulating policies, strategies, plans, and programs related to data protection, and overseeing their implementation.

Second Section: The Impact of Digital Intelligence on Data Privacy and Individual Freedom

Confidentiality and data privacy are important pillars of the transactions upon which digital intelligence systems are based, given the widespread hacking that has begun to invade computer programs and technological designs by hackers.

This requires maintaining the confidentiality of the data entered and used in digital intelligence applications, and to reinforce the right to control the collection and processing of personal information by designated authorities.¹⁵

The right to individual freedom revolves around freedom of choice, independence, and privacy. The individual concerned can reveal or conceal whatever they wish, as long as this information and data is personal and theirs alone.

For instance, in a landmark 1983 ruling, the **German Constitutional Court** recognized the right to informational self-determination as a subset of personal freedom. The court held that:

*"Protecting individuals from unlimited collection, storage, use, and disclosure of personal data falls under the general personal rights enshrined in the German Constitution. This basic right guarantees the individual the authority to decide the extent to which their personal data is revealed and used. Restrictions on the right to privacy are not permitted unless there is a substantial public interest."*¹⁶

The main idea is to give individuals effective control over their personal data. Companies and government institutions must adhere to the key principles related to the processing of personal data, namely transparency, objectivity, integrity, confidentiality, accuracy, limiting objectives, minimizing data, and achieving the public interest.

Third Section: The Role of the Legislative Authority in Regulating the Practice of Digital Intelligence:

Legal regulation plays a key and important role in the world of digital technology in general, and digital intelligence software in particular. This is because the role of legislation is to perform a regulatory function on behalf of society, which is to achieve the public interest and balance among all its segments without discrimination. This demonstrates the role of public law as an indispensable tool for oversight and regulation, given the inability of computers to understand the values, principles, ethics and social norms they operate by. Therefore, the legislature must bridge these gaps safely and fairly.

There are many companies engaged in digital intelligence systems and software do not adhere to ethical and legal standards, resulting in irreparable losses. Here, the state is required to issue permits and licenses related to the possession and use of digital intelligence technologies based on the extent to which those involved adhere to both legal and ethical standards. For example, Amazon was shut down and its licenses revoked due to the use of its technological systems on grounds that promoted gender bias.¹⁷

We conclude by stating that the legislature must establish rules regulating the use of technology and its related fields related to dangerous or prohibited activities. These rules may only be used with the permission of official bodies authorized to issue licenses for their use.¹⁸ Otherwise, anyone who violates them will be subject to accountability and punishment.

According to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, Article (17) states: *"No one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence."*

However, consideration should be given to countries' approach to addressing the use of digital intelligence systems, and their adherence to legal legislation that contributes to preserving the privacy of individuals, institutions, and ordinary companies, uphold international human rights standards, and prevent harm and ethical violations. States must therefore regulate the dissemination of uncontrolled AI systems as they function as **autonomous digital minds**.¹⁹

CHAPTER THREE: THE ROLE OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN REGULATING THE PRACTICE OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE:

Public administration bears dual responsibility: **to promote and safeguard digital intelligence technologies** and **to protect national and economic security**. Therefore, the executive authority must develop strategic plans and objectives that promote progress in the field of digital intelligence, which positively reflects investment encouragement,

sustainable economic development, scientific research, and civil liberties, taking into account privacy and confidentiality. This should be done in cooperation with all private sector institutions, academic circles, and international and regional partners.

Hence, public administration must clearly assign the roles and responsibilities of each entity to ensure the accurate and careful implementation of digital intelligence systems and software, and coordinate among them in accordance with the national strategic plan.²⁰

As for Arab countries, they have not paid much attention to enacting and issuing legislation regulating digital intelligence technologies, organizing them, and advancing them. This is with the exception of a few Arab countries, including the United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Jordan, and others.

In Jordan, for example, a ministry was established to oversee the digital intelligence sector, called the Ministry of Digital Economy and Entrepreneurship. The same is true in the United Arab Emirates, where a Ministry of Artificial Intelligence was established, as well as in Saudi Arabia. In Egypt, the Council of Ministers established a council in 2019 called the National Council for Artificial Intelligence. This council is responsible for developing strategic plans for artificial intelligence, overseeing their implementation, monitoring, and continuous development, in line with global developments. It also works to develop policies and recommendations related to the legal, technical, and economic frameworks related to their implementation. Accordingly, these governments must work to develop an appropriate regulatory environment that is compatible with digital intelligence technologies and their security.

CHAPTER FOUR: DEVELOPMENTS IN LEGAL LIABILITY FOR DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY APPLICATIONS

We will address the developments in legal liability arising from digital intelligence technology applications by explaining this in two sections:

The First Section: The Development of The Concept of Legal Personality for Digital Intelligence Technology.

It is established that legal personality is the legal capacity to acquire rights and assume obligations imposed by law. It is established for a natural person upon birth and life, and is granted to a legal person from a group of persons to achieve a specific goal for which that legal personality was established. The law determines the nature of that legal personality and the methods for establishing it in accordance with its internal regulations. That legal personality shall have a representative who shall oversee its various activities. It is essential for the emergence of a legal person that the state recognizes its legal personality, and from this cornerstone the legal personality begins.

Therefore, digital intelligence devices can be considered a distinct entity that transcends the concept of a machine but does not exceed the limits of human beings. While the human attribute is granted to natural beings, the attribute of legal personality is not limited

to humans alone. Rather, it transcends this restriction, based on the fact that legal personality is not granted to humans as human beings, but rather as those capable of acquiring rights and bearing obligations. Therefore, legal personality is a legal recognition, not a legal innovation.²¹

Furthermore, granting legal personality to digital intelligences, like natural persons, entitles them to many rights that may not be in keeping with their nature. They include the right to life, the right to vote, the right to work, and the right to freedom of expression. These are rights inherent to humans, which is inconsistent with the special nature of digital intelligences. Therefore, digital intelligences cannot be considered natural persons in any way.

Accordingly, a distinction must be made between the human personality that is established for humans and the legal personality based on the ability to acquire rights and bear obligations established for humans and others, similar to the legal person, which has been granted a legal status that defines its nature and its rights and obligations. Accordingly, the concept of legal personality has expanded beyond the physical entity of humans to include the physical entity of non-humans, such as animals (for example, the French Civil Code).

Regarding the recognition of the legal personality of digital intelligence devices, Given the tangible physical existence of a natural person and the intangible legal existence of a legal person, it cannot be said that a legal person exists virtually or legally, given its tangible physical existence. However, its existence is different from the tangible physical existence of a human being, and therefore it cannot be granted legal status under either of these two terms. Not every tangible physical thing has legal personality, but rather the law confers the term "thing" on it.

We note that digital intelligence will create a new generation alongside humans, which necessitates granting it a legal personality that distinguishes it from natural and legal persons and animals.

Autonomous robots can be considered electronic persons responsible for compensating for all damages incurred by others. This clearly means recognizing the legal personality of a robot,²² as adopted by the European Parliament's 2017 decision, stating that a robot must be granted an electronic personality responsible for damages it causes to other parties if it is autonomous in its decisions and interacts with its surrounding environment independently.

Section Two: Adapting Legal Liability Rules to Digital Intelligence

Liability is divided into two main categories: civil liability and criminal liability. The civil and criminal dimensions of this liability are based on the commission of an unlawful act in both cases.

This necessitates examining whether traditional and emerging rules of civil liability can cover the liability of digital intelligence in the event of harm to others, on the one hand,

and within the framework of criminal liability, which relies on punishment, the majority of which is material, on the other hand.

- Civil Liability for Damages Resulting from the Illegal Use of Digital Intelligence:

According to Article (256) of the Jordanian Civil Code No. (43) of 1976, a harmful act or tortious liability is based on three pillars: the harmful act, the damage, and the causal relationship between them. Such liability does not arise and does not require compensation for damages unless the damage was incurred as a result of the harmful act. The general rule of civil liability in Algerian civil law considers anyone who commits a mistake against another, causing them harm, to be liable for compensation, in accordance with Article (214) of the Algerian Civil Code. Accordingly, for civil liability to be established, three elements must be present: mistake, harm, and a causal relationship. Consequently, the basis for establishing civil liability, both contractual and tortious, requires compensation for the harm upon its occurrence.

This prompts us to explore the application of the liability system for the act of guarding objects, as it is well known that Article (2141) of the French Civil Code recognizes that the owner of a thing is its custodian unless proven otherwise. This means that it places the burden of compensating for damages resulting from the thing on its custodian, in exchange for the powers they possess over it through use, direction, and oversight. This is similar to the Algerian legislator, who stipulated in Article (231) of the Algerian Civil Code the three powers of the custodian of a thing: use, management, and oversight.

The same applies to Jordanian civil law. Anyone assigned the custody of mechanical objects and machinery that require special care is liable for any damage caused by these objects unless they prove that the damage was caused by an external cause beyond their control. Egyptian courts have imposed certain duties and obligations on employers, and anyone who uses mechanical machinery or anything that could endanger people's lives or property is considered at fault if they breach these duties or obligations. This perception renders a digital intelligence system subject to the guidance and control of its custodian. This is inconsistent with the structure and nature of intelligent systems, which are characterized by their ability to learn and make independent decisions, making identifying a custodian difficult.²³

It is clear that it is difficult to rely on the theory of liability for the acts of things as a basis for civil liability for damages caused by digital intelligence devices. This prompts us to seek another legal basis for such liability: applying the system of liability for the acts of a defective product to damages resulting from digital intelligence. The burden of compensation falls, depending on the case, either on the designer, or on the manufacturer, whether they manufactured the final product or the components it comprises, or, in exceptional cases, on the owner or user. Although this approach is considered the most appropriate solution for framing liability resulting from damages caused by digital intelligence, it is doubtful that the term "product defect" and the specificity of artificial intelligence as an intangible object raise many difficulties, as the injured party cannot prove the defect of an intangible product.

We note that, given the legislative vacuum in Algerian law regarding civil liability resulting from damages caused by digital intelligence devices, the theory of liability for the acts of a defective product is currently the most applicable theory, despite its shortcomings regarding proving the defect. In this context, the European Parliament moved to establish rules for civil liability for robots in 2017.

This demonstrated the intent of the so-called "human representative" to be responsible, marking the beginning of a legal regulation specific to artificial intelligence. The law recognized the responsibility of the person responsible for the robot, whether the manufacturer or operator, the owner or user, depending on the circumstances of the accident caused by the robot and the degree of actual control the human representative has over the robot. It also called for the creation of a legal entity specific to artificial intelligence that can bear liability in the event of damage through insurance that guarantees compensation.²⁴

- Criminal Liability for Digital Intelligence Offenses

The crime has elements that must be present: a legal element, a material element, and a moral element, including general and specific criminal intent. Without any of these elements, liability is difficult to place on digital intelligence devices. While the material element can be achieved through an error by artificial intelligence devices, the moral element cannot be expected to occur because digital intelligence does not have legal personality, as its will must be directed toward committing the crime intentionally.

Thus, criminal responsibility is established when a person commits an unlawful act and is subject to the appropriate legal penalty. This raises several questions regarding who is criminally responsible: Is it the inventor of the robot? Is the robot itself responsible? Proponents of recognizing the legal personality of digital intelligence devices aim to enable holding them accountable for their personal actions by establishing a financial liability for them, from which those damages can be directly compensated. The second trend has recognized that liability can only be established for a natural person and cannot be established for a digital intelligence. This is due to the inapplicability of most penalties. Furthermore, attributing the crime to a digital intelligence conflict with the principle of the legality of crimes and penalties. Furthermore, the goal of punishment is to achieve general and specific deterrence, which cannot be applied to digital intelligence devices. It is clear that it is difficult to hold a digital intelligence criminally responsible for its harmful actions, given that it is a tool used, despite its ability to mimic humans and the lack of legal texts regulating its liability when any error or damage occurs.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the role of regulatory authorities in governing the use of digital intelligence technology. It provides a comprehensive definition of digital intelligence as: *“Technology that enables machines to exhibit logic and human-like capabilities such as independent decision-making and problem-solving through patterns that simulate human processes.”*

This study also reached a set of findings and recommendations, as follows:

Results

1. Digital intelligence systems represent a tremendous scientific and technological leap that benefits all of humanity if used fairly and objectively and without harming others.
2. Users of smart technology must adhere to the legislation regulating it.
3. Harmonize digital intelligence with work ethics, ensuring that it does not conflict with societal trends, norms, and beliefs.
4. Issuing legislation that achieves its fundamental principles, such as justice, fairness, accountability, non-discrimination, and the rule of law.
5. Developing laws on a timely basis to suit modern technology and the virtual world.
6. General rules are insufficient to apply to digital intelligence, as it is difficult to determine the legal status and consequences thereof.
7. Establishing liability for defective products requires a defect in the product and for the injured party to prove it, which is not possible with digital intelligence technology under the old laws.
8. Digital intelligence technology must be granted legal personality, but with special conditions.
9. The rules governing civil and criminal liability for digital intelligence technology must be adapted to new legal provisions that are in line with the developments in the field of information technology.

Recommendations

1. The need to provide secure databases that comply with legal and judicial provisions, which will positively impact digital intelligence technology systems and technologies.
2. The legislator must develop its current legal system to be consistent with the digital intelligence system.
3. The need to establish government agencies capable of monitoring and tracking suspicious and illegal entities that seek to tamper with, steal, or destroy confidential personal data.
4. Employing disciplined and secure digital intelligence technology in all areas of political, economic, social, scientific, cultural, and security life for the benefit of all humanity.
5. The necessity of formulating a law regulating the use and exploitation of digital intelligence technologies and systems to keep pace with the rapid progress in the field of information technology.
6. Developing strategic plans and training programs to prepare human cadres and support emerging institutions in the field of digital intelligence technology.

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